

Barriers and Enablers of Utilizing social media in SMEs in Sri Lanka for Marketing and Selling

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to identify barriers and enablers of utilizing social media in the SMEs in Sri Lanka for marketing and selling purposes. This study was an exploratory qualitative research and data collection was done utilizing semi-structured interviews with ten SME owners covering seven provinces in Sri Lanka. The thematic analysis was used to analyze the collected data. The findings of the study reflect that participated SME owners use Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp Business, and TikTok with varying success. Also, barriers include poor equipment, human resources, technical knowledge, trust, and internet access. Enablers include cost-effective marketing, customer reach, and brand visibility. Furthermore, the study highlights the need for better tools, internet access, content training, marketing skills, and advertising strategies. Therefore, this study helped to identify primary barriers, enablers, facilities and support needed by SMEs to social media utilization. The findings of this study helped to narrow down the theoretical gap in this domain and provided valuable insights about the barriers, enablers, required support for utilizing social media related to the SMEs in Sri Lanka. The findings of the study also would be useful from a practical point of view when trying to effectively utilize social media in marketing and selling in SMEs in Sri Lanka. There were few limitations for this research such as skipping two provinces due to language issues, varied social media experiences and busy schedules, collecting only the self-reported data, and the gender skewness towards female were the study's major limitations. Also, future research is encouraged to conduct further research focusing on different product and service categories, using mixed method research to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the domain.

Key words: *SME, Social media utilization, Enablers of social media utilization, Social media barriers for SMEs*